

“GEOPOLITICAL SHIFTS AND GEOECONOMIC INTEGRATION IN CENTRAL ASIA: PROSPECTS FOR REGIONAL RESILIENCE AND COOPERATION”**R.Sh. Mirzakhatamov**

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes Central Asia's shift from a geopolitical periphery to an active regional player. It highlights China's growing influence and Asia's rise as key forces reshaping the region's economy and politics. The study outlines opportunities for cooperation and integration, concluding that Central Asia's stability and prosperity rely on pragmatic geo-economic collaboration over geopolitical rivalry.

Introduction

Central Asia is a very complex, contradictory, and ambiguous region. This is its uniqueness, problems, risks and opportunities. Today, the world's leading think tanks have intensified their efforts to forecast the development of the situation in Central Asia and develop strategies for further expanding their influence in the region. Overall, analysts at leading think tanks acknowledge the growing role that Central Asia plays in global politics.

Moreover, this role is interpreted in a somewhat peculiar way: the region it bestows appears not as an independent political player, but as a “battlefield” or “chessboard” for the world's leading powers. Such generalized cliches do not reflect the situation within the region and its changing role in Eurasian geopolitics and geo-economics.

Today, it's clear that Central Asia is gradually emerging from the shadows of global politics and becoming a trending topic, discussed at most authoritative Chinese, Russian, American, European, Turkish, and Indian forums. In early 2016, renowned American researcher F. Fukuyama noted that soon Central Asia would cease to be the periphery of the global economy, becoming its center. The scientist notes the role of China, which is increasingly oriented toward Eurasia, as a fundamental driver of this process. [1]

Fundamentally new trends in regional development have begun to gain momentum in Central Asia, and the level of political trust has increased significantly, allowing for a significant intensification of trade and economic ties between countries. Economic growth will contribute to political stability, and security will be transferred to regional collective mechanisms.

Result

Central Asia is increasingly opening up to the world, becoming part of active global processes. The internal potential and capabilities of the countries in the region, as well as the degree of their cooperation with one another, will determine their place in the global economy and international affairs.

Over the next ten years, the Chinese factor will continue to influence Central Asian economies. Thus, according to forecasts, by 2030, China, which already exerts significant influence on the

economies of Central Asian countries, could lead global economic development.[2] This could significantly change the development paradigm of the Central Asian region.

China's new status as a global player with the world's largest economy presents a major strategic challenge and, at the same time, a major opportunity for Central Asia. In this case, much will be determined by the understanding of the new situation, policies, and aspirations of the countries in the region themselves. Predictions that China will closely monitor domestic political developments in the region and the change of political elites in the Central Asian republics to ensure that they guarantee the protection of Chinese interests are also entirely objective.

If in the past Russia was the sole power determining the region's political fate, in the future this monopoly will be increasingly diluted by a Chinese component. Russia is not reducing its presence in Central Asia (and is unlikely to do so in the next ten years), and China has not yet taken its place, but has already become an indispensable partner for the countries of the region.[3]

According to forecasts, within the next ten years, Asia could surpass Europe and North America in a number of indicators of global power, including population, GDP, investment in technology, and military spending. The vigorous rise of Asian states is expected to restore the power of Greater Asia and reduce Western dominance.[4]

The emergence of new trade routes, the creation of new trade and economic alliances, and the growing flows of goods, capital, and people make it possible to connect continental Eurasia on a qualitatively new basis. As a result of their joint efforts, Central Asian countries are effectively integrating into large-scale continental transport corridors and, together, are forming a powerful logistics hub servicing trade flows between Europe and Asia.

Income and economic growth reflect the economic opportunity for system inclusion. The region is actively pursuing education and awareness. Economic opportunities and inclusion in political life will influence the enlightened development of religion, the reduction of radicalization, and the maintenance of the secular nature of state development. All this helps strengthen the internal stability of the region's states.

This could mean a new opportunity for Central Asia, which will also be affected by the new global economic growth vortex. The question is whether the countries in the region themselves can take advantage of this new historic opportunity for their economies.

Discussion

It is also necessary to clearly understand the challenges currently facing all Central Asian states, which processes will contribute to geopolitical stability and which could lead to the opposite result, and what is the place of each individual state in the overall scheme of interregional interaction?

Central Asian countries are expected to more closely seek potential niches in the international division of labor, which will be determined by the new configuration of trade and investment mega-blocs. New risks will arise for projects to develop Eurasian infrastructure connectivity. With the declining role of natural resources, states that remain outside Western-centric formats

will be even more interested in both developing infrastructure to increase connectivity with Europe and in creating alternative formats of macroregional cooperation – for example, the “One Belt, One Road” [5] initiative.

According to current estimates, Central Asia is now moving in a new direction. One can agree with the conclusion that a major geopolitical shift is taking place in the region, resulting in a change in ties with the Euro-Atlantic community and an increase in China's influence and importance. China is becoming the most significant geopolitical and economic actor in the region. The country's economic presence in Central Asia has increased dramatically, and China's ambitious plans to further expand its influence in Eurasia will have significant consequences – both economically and politically.

Moreover, in the next decade, regional dynamics will have the potential to influence situations beyond their own borders and become a threat to global security. According to forecasts, the Middle East and South Asia are the regions where instability is most likely to increase. South Asia will likely face a series of internal and external shocks over the next 10-15 years. Slow economic growth, complex social dynamics, and energy shortages will pose challenges for Pakistan and Afghanistan.[6] This zone will be a constant irritant for our region as well.

Central Asia will have to coexist with new Asian giants and cooperate with declining powers, which in the coming decades may well begin to settle scores based on the principle of "who's boss" using all available means. The continuing increase in the Asian population (by 2030, Asia will be home to more than 4.94 billion people, or 57.9% of the world's population) [7] also threatens the large, but relatively populous Central Asian countries with obvious migration inconveniences and demographic challenges.

Thus, Central Asia will likely experience increased migration pressure from the South, which, together with the powerful geopolitical turmoil in Asia, will determine the ambiguous cultural, religious, and military environment surrounding the country. In the new strategic environment, our region may have to navigate between geopolitical centers of influence that have the potential to sharply strengthen their position – China, India, Turkey, and others. And it won't be easy to do this.

Over the next ten years, all Central Asian countries will experience a change in political elites. Well-educated, progressive reformers and technocrats with a state-oriented mindset, interested in the development of their countries, are gradually coming to power in the region's republics. The new Central Asian leaders understand the lack of alternative to intraregional cooperation and see a direct link between socio-economic development and cooperation with neighbors. This is not about integration, but rather about closer cooperation based on a balance of regional and national interests. As a result, countries in the region are seeking to redefine and strengthen the common bonds of regional identity, political dialogue, and collective development.

New political, business, and intellectual elites are working together to diversify the economy—on a regional scale. Through a pragmatic division of labor and the utilization of each state's potential, Central Asia is moving away from a raw materials-based model of economic development.

Methodology

The future is impossible to predict: linear forecasting, as a rule, does not produce results. In this work, I used the scenario method. Scenario modeling is a tool for predicting the future, used for medium- and long-term strategic analysis and planning. Scenarios are storylines based on an analysis of real-world trends that describe how the world might look in a given time.

Scenarios do not provide recommendations, and their development is not an end in itself. They stimulate the imagination and provide an intellectual foundation on which to search for new ideas and directions. Scenarios facilitate the development and adoption of more informed and accurate decisions in the context of possible future events and processes. Scenarios are also a practical tool for identifying early warning markers. They are widely used in risk management and strategic planning across a wide range of sectors: scenario approaches allow to identify opportunities, threats, and challenges that, under certain conditions, can turn into opportunities or risks.

Scenario planning does not attempt to predict which future will occur, but through a formalized process identifies a limited set of examples of possible futures that serve as a valuable guide when evaluating current strategy or developing new policies for the future. [8]

Conclusion

Today, Central Asia finds itself at a complex crossroads of opportunities and challenges. The complete collapse or destabilization of the region, which various "experts" have been predicting for many years, is unlikely to occur. As the past 33 years of development have shown, Central Asia, despite its many problems, possesses a certain reserve of internal resilience and a very complex balance.

Each state in the region has its own strengths and weaknesses and can, to varying degrees, take advantage of this new stage. It appears that the next decade is crucial for the entire region and will largely determine the direction of its long-term development. In particular, this period can be compared to the first decade of the development of sovereignty in the Central Asian republics – the foundation was laid on which their statehood was built over the past years.

Our region is becoming the Eurasian epicenter of international activity, a true heartland. To fully realize the potential inherent in the development of Central Asia as a unified region, answers must be found to numerous challenges – both economic and security-related. The region's future prosperity lies in the geo-economics, not geopolitical, realm; this requires pragmatism and cooperation. To fully realize the potential inherent in the development of Central Asia as a unified region, it will be necessary to find solutions to a multitude of challenges – both economic and security-related.

Thus, the dynamics of events occurring in these years in Central Asia allow us to say that in the 21st century the region will experience fundamental changes, unique in their content and scale. One can fully agree with this statement, and it is important to begin trying to understand the nature of the upcoming changes today.

Thus, if we take into account the region's "new opening" to the world and its new positioning in international affairs, then perhaps we should also agree with the forecasts that the transformations Central Asia has undergone in the 20th century is incomparable to what awaits it in the future.

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